

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1990	Yan Shao	2010	2018			Chinese Senior Algorithm Engineer (Computational linguistics)	
1990	Dellis Pratika	2012	No		w	Indonesian Lecturer of Linguistics	
1990	Kosuke Nagata	2012	No			Japanese Asian Modern & Contemporary artist (Arts, Film and New Media)	
1990	Жолудь Анастасия	2012	No		w	Russian Assistant, Department of Romance Philology (literature critic)	
1990	Светлана Анейко	2012	No		w	Belarusian art historian, Deputy General Director for Research and Education	
1990	Şebnem Nazlı Karalı	2013	No		w	Turkish Graduate Student. Studies Philosophy, English Literature, and Existentialism	
1990	Stefan Denda	2014	No			Serbian cultural researcher (Social Geography, Selective forms of tourism, Quality of life research)	
1990	Valida Karimova	2015	No		w	Azerbaijani PhD student in Linguistics (English-American novels, poems, persian-poetry, stories)	
1990	Mirjam Kooiman	2015	No		w	Dutch Curator at Foam Fotografiemuseum (art history)	
1990	Kylie Sago	2015	No		w	French Ph.D. Candidate in Romance Languages and Literatures	
1990	Anela Mulahmetović Ibrišimović	2015	No		w	Bosnian senior assistant of Department of English Language and Linguistics	
1990	Noname	2016			w	nationality	
1990	Amela Delić	2016	No		w	Bosnian Lecturer at Department of Journalism	
1990	Piermatteo Morucci	2019				Italian PhD researcher, Basque Center on Cognition Brain and Language	
1991	Nur Afni Khafsoh	2010			w	Indonesian Lecturer of Sociology of Religion	
1991	Luis Miguel Rojas-Berscia	2011	2019			Italo-Peruvian polyglot linguist	
1991	Ryekotoo Julius Peter	2012	No			Ugandan poet, playwright, novelist, musician, and a language teacher	
1991	Filip Klubička	2012	No			Croatian PhD student in computational linguistics and computational semantics, word meaning and automatic identification of multi-word expressions	
1991	Зайкина Злата Михайловна	2013	2018		w	Russian associate professor of Department Foreign languages	

1991 Thomas Van Hoey	2014	2019		Belgian sinologist and linguist
1991 Saranda Buzhala	2014	2016	w	Albanian Assistant of Albanian Literature
1991 Elsa Vula	2016	2016	w	Albanian Assistant of Albanian language (English Linguistics)
1991 Ratna Istriyani	2016	No	w	Indonesian Lecturer of Religious Sociology
1991 Dan Řezníček	2016	No		Czech Doctoral researcher at LEVYNA Laboratory for the Experimental Research of Religion
1991 Gizem Erginer	2018	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1991 Gretchen McCulloch	2019	No	w	Canadian linguist (pop linguistics and especially internet language)
1992 Michael Terren	2012	No		Australian musician, composer and sound artist
1992 Скачедубова Мария Вадимовна	2013	2019	w	Russian Senior Lecturer in linguistics, Faculty of Humanities
1992 Scarlett Clothier-Goldschmidt	2014	No	w	American linguist (Linguistics, psycholinguist, technical problem solver)
1992 Yilka Imeri	2015	No	w	Albanian Assistant of Albanian language
1992 Harun Zulić	2016	No		Bosnian Educator of Piano, Music and Choir
1992 Shatakshi Singh	2016	No	w	Indian assistant Professor of Amity School of Fine Arts
1992 Joshua D. Weirick	2017	No		American PhD Student in Linguistics
1993 Signe Raudive	2010	No	w	Latvian Research assistant (Cultural Studies, Arts and Humanities, Literature Studies, Cultural Heritage, Digital Humanities)
1993 Стубеда Светлана	2012	2019	w	Belarusian cultural scientist
1993 Fitri Fitri	2014	No	w	Indonesian lecturer of Japanese Linguistic Department
1993 Phuti Sepuru	2015	No	w	South African Lecturer of Music (piano)
1993 Dominique A. Canning	2015	No	w	American PhD Student in Linguistics (sociolinguistics, use of language by marginalized communities)
1993 Antra Upeniece	2015	No	w	Latvian researcher in library science, literacy, local history research, bibliometrics
1993 Katarina Pavicic Ivelja	2015		w	Croatian MA in English Language and Literature and Philosophy
1993 Iza Škrjanec	2016	No	w	Slovenian researcher in Gender studies
1993 Herlina Nurani	2016		w	Indonesian Religious Studies Lecturer
1993 Krista Anna Belševica	2017	No	w	Latvian researcher in Literature, poet
1993 Lorina Pervorfi	2017	No	w	Albanian Assistant of Albanian language

1993 Felix Morgenstern	2018 No		German researcher (ethnomusic)
1993 Aymeric Collart	2018 No		French neurolinguist, PhD student in the Department of English
1993 Justine Mertz	2018 No	w	French PhD student (French Sign Language, phonology, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics)
1994 Kenan Musić	2014 No		Bosnian music Writer, director, actor and blog writer
1994 Mitra Nurul Fitri	2015 No	w	Indonesian linguist
1994 Nicolás José Fernández-Martínez	2017 No		Spanish Lecturer at the department of Languages